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Energy Security Challenges in Nepal: An Econometric Analysis of Electricity Consumption and Production Dynamics

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Abstract

Energy security is very important for Nepal's sustainable development because of its reliance on traditional fuels and hydropower. This study examines Nepal's energy production and consumption and analyzes the factors influencing energy consumption. It analyses the impact of economic growth, electricity production, and population growth on total electricity consumption, identifying key challenges and opportunities. Using secondary data from government sources, the study uses linear, log-linear, and exponential regression models to estimate the relationship between electricity consumption and variables such as real GDP, electricity production, and population. Correlation between energy consumption and real GDP, energy consumption and population growth are found to be positive. Regression results show that economic growth and electricity production are key drivers of electricity consumption whereas the effect of growth on population energy consumption is statistically insignificant. The study suggests the need for robust energy infrastructure, energy diversification, and significant policies for economic growth. Strengthening Nepal's economy and energy production capacity is essential for sustainable economic growth and energy security.

Keywords: Econometric analysis, economic growth, electricity consumption, electricity production, energy security

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